

Validation of the OpenMC model for the AKR-2 research and training reactor using variance reduction techniques

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ABSTRACT

For the simulation of nuclear research reactors, the investigation of physical quantities such as neutron flux and reaction rates can be performed using Monte Carlo (MC) codes. However, obtaining statistically accurate tally estimates in deep shielding problems poses significant challenges in terms of computational power and time constraints. This study explores the application of variance reduction techniques developed in the OpenMC code to evaluate the neutron flux at multiple locations in the AKR-2 zero-power training and research reactor. The survival biasing and weight windows methodologies are employed. These results are then compared to those obtained from an analog simulation. The validation of the simulated results is done through a series of measurements using ³He proportional counters and the activation of manganese foils at the reactor's outer boundary and in two experimental channels. This research demonstrates the applicability of OpenMC's variance reduction capabilities in solving deep penetration problems in a timely manner and provide support for ongoing experimental campaigns at the reactor, such as neutron transmission and spectrum determination.

Keywords: Variance reduction, AKR-2 reactor, OpenMC, deep penetration, validation

1. INTRODUCTION

Accurate estimation of neutron flux and related quantities in nuclear facilities requires the usage of computational simulation tools. These tools are used for heavy-shielded geometries and research reactors, for instance. The AKR-2 training and research reactor at TU Dresden is modelled using the Monte Carlo (MC) codes MCNP, Serpent, and OpenMC [1]. These codes are chosen as modelling tools at the AKR-2 because of their ability to account for complex geometries and use pointwise cross-section libraries.

The reactor is intended to become a facility where codes and methods are validated and nuclear data is measured. Within the NAUTILUS project framework [2], investigations of the reactor's thermal, epithermal, and fast spectra are being conducted using multiple techniques. These techniques include the activation of foils far from the reactor core, the transmission of neutron and gamma particles in the largest experimental channel [3], reactivity-induced transients [4], and time-of-flight measurements [5]. The investigation of the reactor spectrum in multiple locations and the use of the facility as a neutron source for transmission and time-of-flight experiments need support of high-quality simulations.

Validation of the MCNP, Serpent, and OpenMC models of the AKR-2 is currently underway [6]. In this context, this study uses the OpenMC code to estimate the neutron flux at multiple locations in the reactor, exploiting variance reduction techniques to obtain low statistical uncertainty in regions far from the core, where the likelihood that a neutron contributes to the flux is extremely low [7]. The variance reduction methods in OpenMC can be found in the 'OpenMC methods' section of the code documentation. The results obtained are compared with those from analog simulations (i.e. without variance

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reduction) as well as with experimental data. In this paper, section 2 describes briefly the AKR-2 reactor as well as the detectors and techniques used along the measurements performed to validate the simulation results. Section 3 presents the OpenMC detailed model of the AKR-2, together with the description of the detectors and meshes used in the simulations. Section 4 presents the simulated (analog, variance reduction) and experimental results. The results presented demonstrate the applicability of OpenMC variance reduction functions and the MC model of the AKR-2 to the treated problems. Besides, the figure-of-merit (FOM) of the simulations is briefly discussed. Finally, conclusions and future work are described in section 5.

2. THE AKR-2 REACTOR AND THE EXPERIMENT

2.1. Reactor description

The AKR-2 zero-power reactor (see Fig. 1) is operated with a thermal power between 0 and 2 W. Its core consists of two separable cylindrical sections made of plates of a homogeneous mixture of polyethylene and uranium dioxide. When both are joint, the core diameter is 25.0 cm and its height amounts to 27.8 cm. An AmBe startup neutron source is present to obtain sufficient count rate at every reactor state in the power monitors. Three control rods are located in the graphite reflector region. Four experimental channels (7 openings) can be used for samples activation, detector placement, neutron beam extraction, or reactivity variation of the reactor. Shielding in the reactor building is achieved with paraffin and concrete around the reflector region. The outer radius of the concrete boundary is 125 cm.

Figure 1. AKR-2 reactor. (Left) Reactor building. The azimuthal cord from channel 7 (point A) to channel 3-4 and channel 5-6 (point B) is shown. (Right) Main structures at the AKR-2. The plot corresponds to an axial cut of the reactor along the mid plane.

2.2. Instrumentation and measurements

During this experimental campaign, two sets of measurements were performed. In the first, the reduction of the neutron flux in radial direction was investigated. This was done in the channels 3-4 and 5-6. To do so, manganese foils and a ^3He proportional counter detector were used. The manganese foils with 1.2 cm diameter and 70 μm thickness were placed every 10 cm inside of the channel 3-4 into a slitted aluminium bar. The foils were located between the centre of the channel 3-4 and up to 70 cm towards the opening 3 of the channel. After irradiation, their activity was determined using a NaI scintillation detector. The irradiation time was 6 h. Between the position at 70 cm and 225 cm, the ^3He

counter was used to obtain sufficient count rate in both channels 3-4 and 5-6. This implies the measurements were performed at a maximum distance of 1 m from the opening of the channels at the reactor outer boundary. This detector was kept aligned to the channel axis using lasers as shown in the figure 2. The measurement duration at every position for the ^3He detector was such that the relative error of the count rate was below 5%. Outside of the channel, the measurements lasted 60 minutes. The ^3He measurements were dead-time corrected.

The second set of measurements investigated the azimuthal distribution of the neutron flux at the height of the channel 1-2, which is also the height of the centre of the core. These measurements were performed at the reactor boundary covering 180° degrees using the ^3He detector azimuthally every 10 cm .

Figure 2. (Left) Horizontal view of the AKR-2 at the level of channel 3-4. The dark blue dashed line shows the azimuthal positions at the core level. The label "1" represents 180° , while the label "2" indicates 360° . The white arrow represents the axial range of Mn foils' and ^3He detector's locations. The label "3" is at the farthest measurement position at the outlet of channel 3, located 1 m from the reactor boundary. The label "4" is the farthest measurement position at the outlet of channel 4. The label "0" indicates the centre of the channel. The aligned detector, using a laser, in channel 3-4 is shown at top right. The azimuthal position for a given angle of the ^3He detector at the core level height is shown in the figure at the bottom right.

During the measurements, the reactor power was kept at 2 W using the control rod 1 for adjusting reactivity (see figure 2, in violet). An acrylic rod with a diameter of 13 mm and a length of 300 mm was placed in the channel 1-2, close to the reactor core, for the purpose of managing reactivity changes due to temperature feedback. Details about the temperature impact at the AKR-2 and critical control rod positions is found at [6].

3. AKR-2 OPENMC MODEL

In 2023, at the AKR-2, the OpenMC code was adopted to establish a detailed model for teaching and research and to facilitate the accessibility to MC simulations of the reactor to students and external users. The current model mirrors the geometrical and material definitions of the MCNP and Serpent AKR-2 models described in [6].

3.1. Relevant modelling details and settings

The cross section library used in this work is ENDF/B-VIII.0 at 294 K. Control rod 1 (see Fig. 2, in violet) is about half inserted and rod 2 and 3 are fully extracted. Under this configuration, k_{eff} is 1.00170 ± 0.00002 . Deviations from criticality at the used configuration arise from simulating at 294 K, while this configuration is critical at a higher temperature. Furthermore, if other nuclear data libraries are used, differences in k_{eff} up to 200 pcm can be observed. For the purpose of this work, four different mesh detectors were used with the energy-integrated neutron flux as response (see table I).

Table I. Cylindrical mesh bin boundaries definition in OpenMC simulation

Mesh name	Radial (cm)	Azimuthal ($^{\circ}$)	Axial (cm)
"flux weight window"	[0,20,40,...,300]	[0,30,60,...,360]	[0,50,100,120,130,140,150,200,250,300]
"core level"	[0,10,20,...,150]	[180,190,200,...,360]	[127.5,132.5]
"channel 3-4 level"	[0,10,20,...,240]	[0,10,20,...,360]	[135.5,140.5]
"channel 5-6 level"	[0,10,20,...,240]	[0,10,20,...,360]	[119.5,124.5]

The "flux weight window" mesh is used to compute the flux in all the reactor with a coarse mesh to update the weight windows when they are iteratively generated [8]. And the three additional meshes are used to tally the azimuthal and channel results. The centre of the core is at a height of 130 cm with respect to the floor, while the height of channels 3-4 and 5-6 is 122 cm and 138 cm, respectively.

3.2. On the variance reduction implementation

Survival biasing and weight windows (WW) are used to determine the flux in the mentioned meshes. In survival biasing, rather than killing neutrons when absorption occurs, they are kept alive but have their statistical weight reduced. Once the statistical weight falls below a given cut-off weight, the neutron is killed. In WW, particle splitting is used to increase the population of particles in low-flux spatial regions. Once the weight of a particle in a given region falls below the lower bound of the region's weight window, Russian roulette is employed. The generation of WW is done using the Method of Automatic Generation of Importances by Calculation (MAGIC) [8]. Relevant settings for these simulations are displayed in table II.

Table II. Simulation settings in OpenMC

Simulation	Inactive batches	Active batches	Particles/batch	WW - updates
Analog	50	4000	1,000,000	No
Survival biasing	50	4000	1,000,000	No
Weight Windows	40	100	480,000	No/Yes

In survival biasing, the weight cutoff is 0.3, while the weight average is 0.9. In the WW, the maximum number of history splits is 10^7 , without the use of survival biasing simultaneously. The simulations were performed with a number of 32 parallel threads. In order to compare between simulations and experiment, first, the volume-integrated results provided by OpenMC are divided by the volume of the mesh elements. Then, using the location of the measurements, the flux results at the mesh elements which encompass these locations are retrieved from the simulation and compared to the experimental measured values. The azimuthal core level mesh is compared to the azimuthal measurements straightforwardly, but the measurements in the channels 3-4 and 5-6 required the above mentioned post-processing to overcome the impossibility to rotate detectors in OpenMC.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Implementing variance reduction techniques across the entire AKR-2 domain increased the number of events in heavily shielded regions outside of the reactor. Figures 3 and 4 show the increase of the number of neutrons populating regions that are not populated using the analog simulation. In both height levels, it is observed that implementing variance reduction populates to a larger extent the 360° degrees of the reactor. Indeed, using WW yielded non-zero neutron flux everywhere. The flux decreases by eight orders of magnitude from the centre of the core to one meter from the reactor boundary, due to the existence of the concrete and paraffin shielding.

Figure 3. Normalized neutron flux at channel 3-4 height using analog, survival biasing, and WW simulations.

Figure 4. Normalized neutron flux at channel 5-6 height using analog, survival biasing, and WW simulations.

The flux distribution in channels 3-4 and 5-6 is shown in figures 3 and 4. The neutron population increase in low-flux region zones, for instance, between 90° and 180° and between 270° and 360° . However, near the beam channel outlets, the relative error in the neutron flux increased when using WW compared to the analog simulation, due to the decision to run a smaller number of particles and cycles (see table II). This was done to roughly equalize the running times of the analog and WW simulations. This is because the flux estimates in the coarse mesh (see table I), used to generate the WW, have larger values in the experimental channels and the simulation spends more time achieving good statistical accuracy in low-flux regions.

Figures 5 and 6 show an increase in the relative error estimates along the channel 3-4 and 5-6 outside of the reactor boundary when using WW. This is because these regions are not heavily shielded, but are experimental open channels. The survival biasing and analog simulation provide relative errors between 0% and 20%, while the WW increases this value four times. The model qualitatively reproduces the flux decrease in regions far from the channels' centre. The deviations between the experimental and simulated results are due to the incorrect modelling of the heterogeneities in the graphite reflector region, as well as the lack of uncertainty quantification relating to the geometrical and material tolerances. For example, instead of considering single values, the range of densities of graphite and paraffin outside the

Figure 5. Simulated and experimental results of the neutron flux along the experimental channel 3–4.

Figure 6. Simulated and experimental results of the neutron flux along the experimental channel 5–6. $C/E - 1$ values represented at the shaded gray region.

core region need to be considered. This issue will be addressed in future work. In figure 5, experimental results are normalized with respect to the value at the centre of the channel. Towards the opening of channel 4 and in channel 5-6, the measurements were done with the ^3He counters exclusively. In channel 5-6, the results are normalized with respect to the measurement at 65 cm towards the opening 5. The azimuthal results show the effectiveness of the survival biasing and WW to estimate the flux and to decrease the relative error in shielded regions at the reactor. Figure 7 shows that all the azimuthal meshes outside the reactor boundary were populated when using variance reduction techniques. The reduction in the relative error of the azimuthal distribution of the flux is seen in figure 8. In the range of angles considered, the analog calculation had no counts for some meshes, displayed here as 100% relative error. In the survival biasing method, this was reduced slightly. However, a significant improvement is achieved using WW, as the relative error decreased below 20%. Two implementations of WW were done. The non-updated WW and the updated WW. The non-updated WW corresponds

Figure 7. Normalized neutron flux at core height using analog, survival biasing, and WW simulations.

to the estimation of the flux after the generation of a single WW based on the flux results in the coarse mesh. The updated approach uses the results arising from a WW, which is generated using the flux results obtained with the non-updated WW approach. In this way, a second WW is generated using the flux results obtained after the application of an initial WW.

Between 235° and 245° degrees, no significant improvement is made with WW, as this is a region of higher flux, being located between the opening 3 at channel 3-4 and opening 5 at channel 5-6. The model is able to reproduce qualitatively the azimuthal flux results experimentally obtained. However, the bias in figures 5, 6 and 8 above 100% at certain locations demonstrates the need to refine the MC model used here. The shaded region in these figures corresponds to the error metric $C/E - 1$, expressed as a percentage. The required time for the simulation are displayed in table III. For WW, it is displayed the simulation time using the weight window obtained after the flux estimation in the coarse mesh (non-updated WW) and the time using the updated weight window generated with the flux results obtained from the non-updated WW. Considering the FOM in MC simulations as $\frac{1}{\sigma^2 T}$, where σ represents

Figure 8. Results of the azimuthal distribution of neutron flux at core height on the reactor boundary. $C/E - 1$ values represented at the shaded gray region.

the standard deviation and T the simulation time, the performance is substantially increased with using WW. For instance, in the azimuthal results, the increase of time using non-updated WW with respect to the analog simulation is 3.3 times, however, the σ^2 is for most of the angles, reduced 4^2 times. This increase in FOM is valid when using WW for all shielded regions. Using survival biasing does not lead to large improvements in these criticality simulations.

Table III. Simulation time statistics in OpenMC

Simulation	Number of threads	Total simulation time (h)
Analog	32	22.9
Survival biasing	32	55.4
Weight Windows	32	75.4 (non-updated WW); 127.5 (updated WW)

5. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

Variance reduction techniques were implemented in the OpenMC model of the AKR-2 reactor. This allowed us to compute flux estimates in shielded regions. A series of experimental measurements were performed and their results compared to the simulation results along two experimental channels and at the reactor outer boundary covering 180° azimuthally. The simulation results show that the MAGIC methodology can be applied to populate regions of low neutron flux. Additionally, it was shown that the model under validation in OpenMC could qualitatively reproduce the flux attenuation along the reactor channels and the outer boundary. The results indicate the necessity for further improvements in the generation of optimized WW to obtain estimates of neutron spectra outside the reactor for the simulation of, e.g., transmission experiments. At the AKR-2, efforts will continue to obtain experimental data on photon fluence and neutron flux estimates in the vertical direction of the reactor, e.g., at the top lid, to compare them with our variance reduction implementations.

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